

UNRAVELING THE IMPACT OF ETHICAL CULTURE ON WHISTLEBLOWING: A MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS OF ANTECEDENTS, MODERATORS AND CONSEQUENCES IN THE BANKING SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Whistleblowing is an act of identifying and speak about wrongdoing. This study investigates the relationship between ethical culture, leadership, and whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan. A quantitative approach was employed. A survey questionnaire was administered to 210 employees in the banking sector. Grounded in Social Exchange Theory (SET) and Organizational Justice Theory (OJT), this study explores the antecedents, moderators, and consequences of whistleblowing, providing insights into the dynamics of ethical culture and whistleblowing. The findings of this study support the hypotheses that ethical culture, leadership, and organizational reputation are significant predictors of whistleblowing, and that moral courage and organizational virtuousness moderate the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing. The results of this study indicate that ethical culture, leadership, and organizational reputation are significant predictors of whistleblowing. The study also found that moral courage and organizational virtuousness moderate the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing. The findings of this study contribute to our understanding of the complex relationships between ethical culture, leadership, and whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan. The study's results have important implications for policymakers, managers, and researchers. The findings suggest that organizations should prioritize the development of a strong ethical culture and leadership to encourage whistleblowing. The study's results also highlight the importance of moral courage and organizational virtuousness in promoting whistleblowing.

Keywords: whistleblowing, ethical culture, leadership, organizational reputation, moral courage, organizational virtuousness, banking sector, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

In order to expose frauds and other forms of organizational misconduct, whistleblowers are essential. According to recent data on workplace fraud cases in businesses, half of all fraud cases in Latin America are discovered thanks to tips from people who witness misbehavior (Association of Certified Fraud Examiners, 2020). Furthermore, by disclosing wrongdoing, whistleblowers can assist companies in preventing monetary losses (like staff

embezzlement), legal actions (like employee discrimination or moral assault charges), and harm to their reputation (Near & Miceli, 2016). Whistleblowers assisted in the recovery of about \$4 billion in false charges in the United States during the 2017 fiscal year (U.S. Department of Justice, 2017).

The banking sector, a cornerstone of modern economies, has witnessed numerous scandals and

unethical practices in recent years (e.g., Libor scandal, Wells Fargo fake accounts scandal). These incidents not only eroded public trust but also highlighted the importance of ethical culture in promoting whistleblowing and preventing wrongdoing (Kaptein, 2011; Treviño et al., 2014). Whistleblowing, defined as the disclosure of organizational wrongdoing by an insider (Near & Miceli, 1985), is a crucial mechanism for detecting and preventing unethical behavior.

According to research, whistleblowing intentions and practices are significantly influenced by ethical culture (Kaptein, 2011; Treviño et al., 2014). Clarity, congruency, feasibility, supportability, transparency, discussability, and sanctionability are some of the dimensions that make up an ethical culture (Kaptein, 2008). However, there are several variables that affect the association between ethical culture and whistleblowing, such as peer ethical conduct, organizational virtuousness, moral bravery, ethical leadership, and corporate reputation (Brown et al., 2005; Detert et al., 2008). Pakistan has been repeatedly described as a developing nation that is rife with corruption. According to a 2015 Transparency International report, Pakistan was placed 117th out of 168 nations with a score of 30 (TI, 2015). The absence of a whistleblower mechanism was one of the main shortcomings identified in another research that evaluated Pakistan's national integrity system (TI, 2014). In Pakistan, whistleblowing is still not a common practice in businesses, and there is even less research on the subject. Regulations and laws are continuously being developed.

This study aims to unravel the impact of ethical culture on whistleblowing in the banking sector, using a multilevel analysis framework. Drawing on organizational justice theory (Greenberg, 1990) and social exchange theory (Emerson, 1976), this study will investigate the relationships between ethical culture, moral courage, organizational virtuousness, and whistleblowing. Specifically, this study will examine the moderating roles of moral courage and organizational virtuousness in the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing.

2- Theoretical Background and Hypotheses

2.1 Whistleblowing

Whistleblowing, the act of reporting unethical, illegal, or improper conduct within an organization, is a significant mechanism for

maintaining organizational accountability and ethical standards. Theoretical perspectives on whistleblowing provide insights into the psychological, social, and organizational factors that drive or hinder this behavior.

2.1.1 Organizational Justice Theory:

This theory emphasizes the role of fairness in organizational processes and outcomes (Greenberg, 1990). Whistleblowing often occurs when employees perceive injustices within their workplace, whether distributive (fairness of outcomes), procedural (fairness of processes), or interactional (fairness in interpersonal treatment). Employees are more likely to blow the whistle when they believe their actions will contribute to rectifying unfair practices and when they trust the organization to handle reports of misconduct justly. Conversely, perceived injustice can discourage whistleblowing if employees fear retaliation or believe their concerns will be ignored (Near & Miceli, 1995).

2.1.2 Social Exchange Theory

This theory explains the reciprocal relationship between employees and their organization (Emerson, 1976). Whistleblowing can be viewed as an exchange process where employees report misconduct in exchange for an ethical and accountable work environment. However, when the organization fails to uphold its part of the exchange—by fostering a culture of trust, fairness, and support—employees may feel demotivated to report unethical behavior. Positive exchanges, such as recognition for ethical behavior and assurance of protection for whistleblowers, enhance the likelihood of whistleblowing (Kaptein, 2011).

2.2 Ethical Culture

Organizational justice theory (Greenberg, 1990) suggests that employees' perceptions of fairness in the workplace influence their attitudes and behaviors. Ethical culture, a dimension of organizational justice, refers to the shared values and norms that promote ethical behavior within an organization (Kaptein, 2008).

H 1: Ethical culture will significantly influence on whistleblowing.

Ethical culture, comprising sub-dimensions like clarity, congruency, feasibility, supportability, transparency, discussability, and sanctionability, is

vital for establishing an environment that supports ethical decision-making. Kaptein (2008) asserts that these dimensions collectively define an organization's ability to encourage ethical behavior and discourage misconduct. An ethical culture provides clear behavioral expectations, aligns policies with actions, and supports open discussions on ethics. According to organizational justice theory (Greenberg, 1990), an ethical culture enhances perceptions of procedural and distributive justice, fostering employees' trust and fairness perceptions.

2.2.1 Clarity and Whistleblowing

Clarity in organizational culture is crucial for ethical behavior, as it provides clear expectations for employee conduct. Without clear guidelines, employees may struggle to distinguish between ethical and unethical behavior (Kaptein, 2008). Research suggests that ambiguity in moral expectations can lead to unethical conduct (Bird & Waters, 1989; Jackson, 2000; Tyler & Blader, 2005). Clear communication, on the other hand, reduces the chances of unethical behavior (Jubb, 1999) and fosters a sense of procedural justice, encouraging ethical conduct and whistleblowing. According to Organizational Justice Theory, clarity in expectations aligns with fairness, providing a transparent framework for understanding acceptable behaviors. Social Exchange Theory also suggests that clear guidelines promote positive exchanges between the organization and its members, encouraging them to report wrongdoing without fear of retaliation.

Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1a: Clarity in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis suggests that greater clarity in the communication of ethical expectations within an organization enhances the likelihood of employees engaging in whistleblowing, as they are more aware of what is considered unethical behavior and feel more confident in reporting it in alignment with organizational norms.

2.2.2 Congruency and Whistleblowing

Consistency between organizational values and leadership behavior is crucial for promoting ethical conduct. When leaders model ethical expectations, employees receive consistent signals that enhance their trust and adherence to the ethical framework.

In contrast, inconsistent leadership can lead to unethical behaviors.

The theory of value congruence (Enz, 1988) suggests that employees are more empowered and committed when their values align with those of the organization and its leaders. Research highlights that employees often emulate their leaders' behavior and look to them as role models for appropriate conduct (Hegarty & Sims, 1978; Brown, Treviño, & Harrison, 2005; Schminke, Ambrose, & Neubaum, 2005).

Organizational Justice Theory and Social Exchange Theory further emphasize the importance of congruency in leadership behavior. Congruency reflects fairness, motivating employees to act ethically and report wrongdoing. It also builds trust and positive relational exchanges, encouraging employees to contribute positively to the organization, including whistleblowing.

Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1b: Congruency in management behavior (local and senior) with organizational ethical culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis implies that when management demonstrates alignment with organizational norms through their behavior, employees are more likely to engage in whistleblowing, as they feel supported and confident that their actions align with organizational expectations.

2.2.3 Feasibility and Whistleblowing

Feasibility, as a dimension of ethical organizational culture, pertains to the extent to which employees are provided with adequate resources, information, authority, and support to fulfill their responsibilities effectively. When organizations ensure timely access to these resources, employees are better equipped to meet their performance objectives and are more likely to engage in ethical behavior, including whistleblowing. Conversely, a lack of feasibility—manifested through insufficient resources or excessive performance pressures—can increase the risk of misconduct and decrease employees' willingness to report unethical behavior. Under such circumstances, employees may prioritize meeting targets over addressing ethical concerns, or they may feel disempowered and perceive whistleblowing as a task outside their scope of responsibility (Kaptein, 1998, 2011).

Low feasibility can also hinder the reporting process itself. When employees and management

are overburdened with tasks, opportunities for discussing and addressing misconduct diminish. This dynamic may lead employees to adopt a passive approach, believing that raising concerns is neither feasible nor their responsibility. Kaptein (1998) highlights that inadequate resources, information, or authority can foster negligence, further exacerbating the risk of unethical behavior. From the perspective of Organizational Justice Theory, feasibility contributes to perceptions of procedural fairness. Employees who feel adequately resourced are more likely to perceive the organization as equitable and supportive, which fosters trust and ethical accountability. This sense of fairness can motivate employees to engage in whistleblowing as a way to uphold organizational integrity. Similarly, Social Exchange Theory posits that when organizations provide employees with the necessary tools and authority to perform their roles, it strengthens the relational exchange. Employees, in turn, reciprocate by taking actions that protect and benefit the organization, such as reporting misconduct.

Based on these insights, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1c: Feasibility in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis asserts that when organizations ensure sufficient resources, timely information, and support for employees, they create an environment conducive to ethical behavior and encourage whistleblowing by removing barriers that might otherwise hinder employees from reporting unethical practices.

2.2.4 Supportability and Whistleblowing

Supportability, as a dimension of ethical organizational culture, emphasizes the organization's role in creating an environment where employees feel valued, supported, and encouraged to adhere to ethical principles. When employees perceive a lack of support, mistrust, or inequity in their workplace, they are more likely to feel demoralized and dissatisfied, which can lead to unethical behavior or even deliberate harm to the organization as a form of retribution (Kaptein, 1998, 2008). Conversely, employees who feel supported and encouraged to identify with the organization's values are more likely to align their behavior with ethical standards, as demonstrated

in the empirical findings of Tyler and Blader (2005).

Supportability also fosters a sense of organizational identification and commitment, which strengthens employees' emotional investment in upholding ethical norms. Employees who strongly identify with their organization view unethical behavior by others as a threat to their own sense of identity and are more likely to take action, such as whistleblowing, to address such transgressions (Den Nieuwenboer, 2008). In this context, supportability reflects not only the provision of resources and encouragement but also the cultivation of trust, fairness, and a collaborative atmosphere that motivates employees to safeguard organizational integrity.

From the perspective of **Organizational Justice Theory**, supportability underscores the importance of fairness in the treatment of employees. When employees perceive that they are treated equitably and are supported in their ethical decisions, they are more likely to trust organizational processes and report unethical behavior. Similarly, **Social Exchange Theory** suggests that the organization-employee relationship is reciprocal. When organizations invest in fostering a supportive ethical environment, employees feel an obligation to reciprocate by engaging in behaviors that benefit the organization, such as whistleblowing to prevent harm or misconduct.

Based on this understanding, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1d: Supportability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis suggests that when employees perceive a supportive ethical environment that encourages their identification with organizational values and norms, they are more likely to engage in whistleblowing to protect the integrity of the organization.

2.2.5 Transparency and Whistleblowing

As a component of an ethical culture, transparency is crucial in influencing employees' choices to come forward with information. Employees are more inclined to engage in internal reporting, a tool for promoting organizational openness, when they think it will provide just and efficient results, especially when it comes to resolving problems that management is unaware of (Miceli et al., 2008). Employees are less inclined to disclose misconduct,

though, if they believe that management is already aware of it. By ensuring that workers understand the repercussions of their actions, transparency motivates them to accept accountability and change unethical behavior (Bovens, 1998).

Without this clarity, employees may focus solely on their immediate actions, ignoring the broader implications of their conduct.

From the lens of **Organizational Justice Theory**, transparency is closely tied to perceptions of fairness. Employees are more likely to report misconduct when they believe their organization values openness and ensures just outcomes for whistleblowers. Transparency strengthens trust in organizational processes, making whistleblowing a viable and trusted mechanism for addressing unethical behavior. Similarly, **Social Exchange Theory** suggests that when organizations promote transparency, employees feel obligated to reciprocate by upholding the ethical standards of the workplace, including reporting misconduct. Transparency cultivates a sense of collective responsibility, as employees recognize that their ethical actions contribute to maintaining organizational integrity.

Based on these insights, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1e: Transparency in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis asserts that when organizations cultivate a transparent culture where employees and managers can observe and understand the consequences of their actions, employees are more likely to report unethical behavior to maintain and enhance the existing levels of transparency.

2.2.6 Discussability and Whistleblowing

Discussability, as an ethical virtue in organizational culture, refers to the opportunities employees have to openly raise, analyze, and discuss ethical concerns without fear of reprisal. Kaptein (1998, 2008, 2011) emphasizes that low discussability within an organization fosters a culture of silence, where employees hesitate to address ethical dilemmas or misconduct. In such environments, unethical behavior often goes unchecked, as employees may engage in practices like blocking negative information (Bishop, 1991), suppressing criticism (Kirrane, 1990), and avoiding difficult conversations (Cooke, 1991). These behaviors hinder the organization's ability to learn from

mistakes, perpetuating a culture of unethical behavior and missed opportunities for improvement.

From the perspective of **Organizational Justice Theory**, discussability aligns with the principle of interactional justice, where employees feel respected and valued when they can voice their concerns without fear of retaliation. An open and supportive communication culture reinforces trust in organizational processes, making employees more likely to engage in whistleblowing. **Social Exchange Theory** also supports the role of discussability, as organizations that encourage open communication foster a sense of psychological safety and trust. Employees, in turn, are more inclined to reciprocate by reporting misconduct to uphold the organization's ethical standards. Based on this understanding, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1f: Discussability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis suggests that when organizations foster an open environment where ethical issues can be discussed freely and without fear, employees are more likely to report misconduct, contributing to a transparent and accountable workplace.

2.2.7 Sanctionability and Whistleblowing

Sanctionability, as an ethical virtue of organizational culture, refers to the consistent enforcement of consequences for unethical behavior and recognition of ethical conduct. Kaptein (1998, 2008) highlights that tolerance for unethical behavior creates a perception that such conduct will go unpunished or even be implicitly encouraged, leading to a proliferation of unethical practices. On the other hand, when wrongdoings are met with appropriate sanctions and ethical actions are rewarded, organizations foster an environment that encourages employees to act ethically and report misconduct.

From the perspective of **Organizational Justice Theory**, sanctionability aligns with both procedural and distributive justice. When employees observe consistent and fair enforcement of sanctions, they perceive the organization as just, which fosters trust in its ethical processes. This perception motivates employees to report unethical behavior, as they believe their efforts will contribute to a fair and ethical workplace. **Social Exchange Theory** also supports this dynamic by

emphasizing reciprocal relationships. When organizations demonstrate fairness by rewarding ethical conduct and sanctioning misconduct, employees feel a sense of obligation to reciprocate by reporting unethical practices to maintain the organization's integrity.

Based on these theoretical underpinnings, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1g: Sanctionability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

This hypothesis suggests that when organizations consistently enforce sanctions for unethical behavior and reward ethical actions, employees are more likely to report misconduct, fostering a culture of accountability and ethical integrity.

2.3 Ethical Leadership

Ethical leadership refers to leaders who demonstrate and promote ethical behavior through their actions and decisions. Brown and Treviño (2006) emphasize that ethical leaders foster trust, fairness, and transparency, encouraging employees to emulate ethical behavior. Using social exchange theory (Emerson, 1976), employees perceive ethical leaders as trustworthy and reciprocate by engaging in organizationally beneficial behaviors like whistleblowing. Ethical leadership also supports Kaptein's (2008) ethical culture framework by influencing dimensions such as clarity, congruency, and transparency.

H2: Ethical leadership significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

2.4 Organizational Reputation

Organizational reputation reflects stakeholders' perceptions of an organization's integrity and accountability. Employees in organizations with strong reputations are more likely to report unethical behavior to maintain this image. According to organizational justice theory, reputation enhances perceptions of fairness and moral obligation, motivating employees to uphold ethical standards (Bitektine, 2011). Social exchange theory also suggests that a strong reputation fosters loyalty and ethical reciprocity, leading to higher whistleblowing intentions.

H3: Organizational reputation significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

2.5 Peer Ethical Behavior

Peer ethical behavior refers to colleagues' adherence to ethical standards and practices. Employees often model their behavior based on peer actions, aligning with Bandura's (1977) social learning theory. In the context of whistleblowing, when peers exhibit ethical behavior, it normalizes reporting misconduct. The dimensions of ethical culture, such as discussibility and supportability, are strengthened by peer behavior, promoting a collective commitment to ethics.

H4: Peer ethical behavior significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

2.6 Moral Courage (Moderator)

Moral courage represents an individual's ability to face ethical challenges despite personal risks. It moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing by amplifying employees' willingness to act on ethical concerns. According to organizational justice theory, moral courage strengthens perceptions of fairness by demonstrating that ethical behavior is rewarded, not penalized (Hannah et al., 2011).

H5: Moral courage moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing, such that the relationship is stronger when moral courage is high.

2.7 Organizational Virtuousness (Moderator)

Workplace behaviors that foster honesty, empathy, and forgiveness are all part of organizational virtue. In order to promote whistleblowing, virtuous businesses foster an atmosphere that supports ethical culture elements like discussibility and sanctionability. Employees are more inclined to report misconduct when they believe that the company is committed to ethics, according to social exchange theory (Cameron et al., 2004).

H6: Organizational virtuousness moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing, such that the relationship is stronger when organizational virtuousness is high.

The evidence highlights the critical role of ethical culture, leadership, and organizational mechanisms in promoting whistleblowing. In the banking sector, particularly in Pakistan, addressing

barriers like peer ethical behavior and cultural resistance is key. These findings align with your thesis framework and provide robust support for the relationships and moderators you're exploring. This review highlights the complex interplay between ethical culture, leadership, and individual factors like moral courage in promoting whistleblowing. In the banking sector of Pakistan, addressing barriers like fear of retaliation and strengthening ethical leadership are pivotal. These insights align closely with your thesis objectives, offering robust evidence to support your study. This empirical review underscores the intricate dynamics of ethical culture, leadership, and individual factors like moral courage in promoting

whistleblowing. While the banking sector in Pakistan presents unique challenges, fostering ethical leadership, enhancing transparency, and mitigating fear of retaliation are key strategies for improving whistleblowing rates.

The empirical literature underscores the significance of ethical culture, leadership, reputation, and peer ethical behavior in fostering whistleblowing. Moderators such as moral courage and organizational virtuousness amplify these relationships. Whistleblowing in the banking sector requires robust ethical frameworks, supported by organizational justice and social exchange principles, to mitigate fear and encourage ethical behavior.

3-Research Method

Ethical Culture

Figure 3.1 Proposed Conceptual Framework

3.1 Research Approach

The research approach for this study will be quantitative, as it aims to investigate the relationships between ethical culture, moral courage, organizational virtuousness, and whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan (Creswell, 2014). A quantitative approach will allow for the collection and analysis of numerical data, enabling the testing of hypotheses and the

identification of correlations between variables. This approach allows for testing hypotheses about the impact of various independent variables (e.g., ethical culture, ethical leadership, organizational reputation, peer ethical behavior) on the dependent variable (whistleblowing) while accounting for the moderating effects of moral courage and organizational virtuousness.

3.2 Research Design

The research design for this study will be a cross-sectional survey design, as it aims to collect data from a sample of respondents at a single point in time (Bryman, 2016). This design will enable the collection of data on the relationships between variables.

Descriptive and Correlational Research Design

This study requires **descriptive** and **correlational** research designs. The **descriptive design** will help in profiling the current state of ethical culture in the banking sector, while the **correlational design** will allow you to explore the relationships between ethical culture and whistleblowing, considering moderating effects.

3.3 Sampling Design

The sampling design for this study will be a non-probability sampling design, specifically a convenience sampling design (Etikan et al., 2016). This design will involve selecting a sample of respondents from the banking sector of Pakistan who are easily accessible and willing to participate in the study.

3.3.1 Target Population

The target population for this study will be employees working in the banking sector of Pakistan (State Bank of Pakistan, 2022). This population will include employees from various levels and departments within the banking sector.

3.3.1.1 Sample Size

The sample size for this research endeavor will be determined by the total number of respondents collected. While screening the data, it can be found that some of the responses will either filled out incorrectly or incompletely. Consequently, those responses will be excluded from the sample, and the final sample size for data analysis will remain at 300. The investigation will employ the purposive sampling technique. By employing the non-probability sampling method, the researcher deliberately chooses specific units from the population based on their similarities, focusing on the sample required for this study. Consequently, the researcher can sustain a smaller sample size instead of enlarging it.

3.3.2 Sample Techniques

The sample techniques for this study will involve distributing online surveys and hard copy of questionnaire to employees working in the banking sector of Pakistan (Etikan et al., 2016). The surveys will be distributed through email and social media platforms, and respondents will be asked to complete the survey voluntarily.

Convenience sampling have been used in the following study. Convenience sampling involves selecting individuals who are readily accessible to the researcher. Convenience sampling selects people who are easily reachable by the researcher. Although this approach a practicable and economical, it is important to acknowledge that it might introduce bias as samples may not accurately represent the entire population. In exploratory investigations where access to the target population is restricted, it is frequently employed. This is a frequently employed strategy utilized by researchers who are constrained by limited time, either due to finding constraints or limited access to the target group. It is highly effective when the main goal is to obtain data rapidly and efficiently.

The researcher chose variables such as gender, age, designation, organization and number of working years from a convenient sample of individuals, rather than using a random or systematic sampling method.

3.4 Instrument

The instrument for this study will be a self-administered online survey and hard copy of questionnaire, A **structured questionnaire** will be the primary data collection instrument. It will consist of closed-ended questions designed to measure ethical culture with sub-variables, ethical leadership, organizational reputation, peer ethical behavior, moral courage, organizational virtuousness, and whistleblowing. Standardized scales for each construct will be adapted or developed, ensuring reliability and validity. seven-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 7=strongly agree) will be used for all variables.

3.4.1 Whistleblowing (Park et al., 2005).

The dependent variable is whistleblowing, which will be assessed by looking at how employees feel about reporting misconduct or keeping quiet about it. A sample item "Blowing the whistle would help prevent serious harm to the organization." is taken from Park et al. (2005).

3.4.2 Ethical culture (Kaptein, 2008)

Ethical culture will be taken as independent variable for the study and it will be measured by using Corporate Ethical Virtues Model (CEVMS) this model was proposed by Kaptein(2008),it define the different dimensions of corporate ethical culture virtues and it makes sure employees' psychological wellbeing and safety when they report any wrongdoing. Ethical culture is supported by ethical conduct in organizations, will be measured in terms of how ethical culture motivate employees to report wrongdoings.

3.4.3 Moral courage (May et al. (2014))

Four items created by May et al. (2014) will be used to evaluate moral bravery. "I would prefer to remain in the background even if a coworker is being taunted or talked about unfairly," was a sample items. High validity and reliability have been shown for this scale (Cheng et al., 2019; Comer and Schwartz, 2017).

3.4.4 Organizational virtuousness (Cameron et al., 2004)

Using a 15-item scale taken from Cameron et al. (2004), organizational virtuousness will be assessed. Statements such as "This is a forgiving,

compassionate Organization in which to work" will be given to employees. In previous studies by Sun and Yoon (2020) and Gukiina et al. (2018).

3.4.5 Ethical leadership (Brown et al., 2005)

A ten-item scale that was modified from Brown et al. (2005) will be used to measure ethical leadership in order to gauge how employees feel about their leaders' moral conduct. "My managers can be trusted," read one of its sample items. The reliability of this scale has been demonstrated by recent investigations (Schwepker and Dimitriou, 2021; Fan et al., 2021; Bhatti et al., 2020).

3.4.6 Organizational reputation (J. Agarwal et al 2014)

Organizational reputation will be measured using 20 item scales adopted from(J. Agarwal et al 2014). A sample item is "I admire and respect this organization."

3.4.7 Peer ethical behavior (Mayer et al. (2013)

To measure peer ethical behavior three items will be adapted from Mayer et al. (2013). A sample item is: "My peers carefully consider ethical issues when making work-related decisions." We average the three items to compute the "Peers" score.

Table No.3.1 Sample items

S.No	Variables	No. of Items	Reliability	Sample Items
1-	Whistleblowing (Park et al., 2005)	17	0.993	Blowing the whistle would help prevent serious harm to the organization.
2-	CEVMS (Kaptein, 2008) Ethical culture Clarity	10	0.887	The organization makes it sufficiently clear to me how I should deal with confidential information responsibly.
	Congruency	10	0.849	My supervisor is honest and reliable.
	Feasibility	6	0.785	In order to be successful in my organization, I sometimes have to sacrifice my personal norms and values.
	Supportability	6	0.924	In my immediate working environment, everyone treats one another with respect.
	Transparency	7	0.839	If my manager does something which is not permitted, someone in the organization

				will find out about it.
	Discussability	10	0.734	In my immediate working environment, reports of unethical conduct are handled with caution.
	Sanctionability	8	0.854	In my immediate working environment, ethical conduct is valued highly.
3-	Ethical leadership	10	0.863	My managers can be trusted.
4-	Peer Ethical Behavior	3	0.741	My peers carefully consider ethical issues when making work-related decisions.
5-	Organizational Reputation	20	0.901	I admire and respect this organization.
6-	Moral courage	4	0.802	I would prefer to remain in the background even if a coworker is being taunted or talked about unfairly.
7-	Organizational Virtuousness	15	0.923	This is a forgiving, compassionate Organization in which to work.

3.5 Statistical Technique

Various statistical approaches are used in the data analysis process, SPSS was used to identify missing values and outliers and efficiently remove all pollutants from the data during the current data screening phase. SPSS, a widely used statistical application, is typically employed for initial data

analysis activities such as examining data distributions and validating missing values. PLS-SEM is employed in data analysis to assess the measurements and substantive models of the investigation, as well as to investigate the connections between the constructs in the proposed research model.

4-Results

4.1 Data Screening

4.1.1 Respondents' Demographics

Table 4.1.1 Statistics

		Statistics			
		Gender	Experience	Qualification	Age
N	Valid	210	210	210	210
	Missing	0	0	0	0

Table 4.1.2 Gender

		Gender			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Male	153	72.9	72.9	72.9
	Female	57	27.1	27.1	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	100.0	

In this research study 210 respondents participated out of which 153 are male and 57 are female as the

above table shows that 72.9% are male and 27.1% are female respectively.

Table 4.1.3 Experience

		Experience			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	less than 5 years	60	28.6	28.6	28.6
	more than 5 years	150	71.4	71.4	100.0
Total		210	100.0	100.0	

Furthermore, in experience 60 respondents have less than 5 years experience and 150 respondents have more than 5 years experience out of 210.

Table 4.1.4 Qualification

		Qualification			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Graduation	55	26.2	26.2	26.2
	Master	145	69.0	69.0	95.2
	above masters	10	4.8	4.8	100.0
Total		210	100.0	100.0	

In this research study, in qualification 55 respondents are graduated and 145 are masters and 10 respondents are above masters out of 210, as the above table shows 26.2 %,69.0% and 4.8% are graduate, masters and above masters respectively

Table 4.1.5 Age

		Age			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Under 30	10	4.8	4.8	4.8
	30-40	15	7.1	7.1	11.9
	40-50	175	83.3	83.3	95.2
	above 50	10	4.8	4.8	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	100.0	

In this research study the respondents' age who participated are 10 respondents under 30,15 participants are between 30-40 years age ,175 are between 40-50 years and 10 participants are above 50 years of age, in percentage 4.8,7.1,83.3 and 4.8 are under 30,30-40,40-50 and above 50 respectively.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics (Descriptive profile of the data)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error	Kurtosis	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic		Statistic	
Whistleblowing	210	64.2563	2.63251	6.930	-.356	.168	.305	.334
Clarity	210	5.6910	.57754	.334	-1.737	.168	1.709	.334
Congruency	210	5.7590	.66652	.444	-2.723	.168	6.674	.334
Feasibility	210	3.0230	.34873	.122	.812	.168	2.857	.334
Supportability	210	5.7952	.90240	.814	-4.119	.168	17.410	.334
Transparency	210	5.7762	.89785	.806	-3.908	.168	15.503	.334
Discussability	210	5.8052	.80371	.646	-4.007	.168	16.653	.334
Sanctionability	210	5.8048	.75456	.569	-4.652	.168	22.724	.334
Ethical leadership	210	5.8429	.73795	.545	-5.079	.168	26.121	.334
Peer Ethical Behavior	210	5.8381	.62826	.395	-4.656	.168	22.875	.334
Organizational Reputation	210	5.8200	.71595	.513	-4.730	.168	23.127	.334
Moral Courage	210	3.9917	.23885	.057	-2.725	.168	23.081	.334
Organizational Virtuousness	210	5.8111	.68369	.467	-3.391	.168	9.699	.334
Valid N (list wise)	210							

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the study variables are presented in Table. The results show that the mean scores for the variables ranged from 3.02 (Feasibility) to 64.26 (Whistleblowing), indicating varying levels of perceptions and attitudes among the respondents. The standard deviations ranged from 0.24 (Moral Courage) to 2.63 (Whistleblowing), suggesting differing degrees of variability across the variables. Skewness values

indicated that some variables, such as Congruency and Supportability, had asymmetric distributions, while kurtosis values revealed non-normal distributions for certain variables, including Congruency and Sanctionability. Overall, the descriptive statistics provide a snapshot of the central tendency and variability of the study variables, serving as a foundation for further analysis and interpretation.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Construct	Item	Loading	CR	AVE
W			0.993	0.338
	W1	0.893		
	W2	.776		
	W3	.902		
	W4	.604		

CL	W5	.141	0.887	0.711
	W6	.348		
	W7	.631		
	W8	.751		
	W9	.158		
	W10	.106		
	W11	.854		
	W12	.847		
	W13	.587		
	W14	.510		
CO	W15	.701		
	W16	.390		
	W17	.715		
	CL1	.301		
	CL2	.582		
	CL3	.933		
	CL4	.481		
	CL5	.756		
	CL6	.938		
	CL7	.930		
F	CL8	.960		
	CL9	.958		
	CL10	.934		
	CO1	.967		
	CO2	.971		
	CO3	.984		
	CO4	.962		
	CO5	.978		
	CO6	.968		
	CO7	.966		
SU	CO8	.986		
	CO9	.945		
	CO10	.984		
	F1	.818		
	F2	.380		
	F3	.493		
	F4	.628		
	F5	.570		
	F6	.863		
	SU1	.980		
T	SU2	.980		
	SU3	.980		
	SU4	.980		
	SU5	.980		
	SU6	.980		
	T1	.983		
T2	.983			
T3	.983			
			0.849	0.623
			0.785	0.441
			0.924	0.703
			0.839	0.571

D	T4	.983	0.734	0.501
	T5	.983		
	T6	.983		
	T7	.983		
	D1	.650		
	D2	.946		
	D3	.946		
	D4	.946		
SA	D5	.946	0.854	0.584
	D6	.946		
	D7	.946		
	D8	.946		
	D9	.946		
	D10	.946		
	SA1	.911		
	SA2	.911		
	SA3	.911		
	SA4	.911		
EL	SA5	.911	0.863	0.541
	SA6	.911		
	SA7	.911		
	SA8	.911		
	EL1	.929		
	EL2	.929		
	EL3	.929		
	EL4	.929		
	EL5	.929		
	EL6	.929		
PEB	EL7	.929	0.741	0.479
	EL8	.929		
	EL9	.929		
OR	EL10	.929	0.901	0.636
	PEB1	.718		
	PEB2	.718		
	PEB3	.718		
	OR1	.718		
	OR2	.990		
	OR3	.990		
	OR4	.990		
	OR5	.990		
	OR6	.990		
	OR7	.990		
	OR8	.990		
	OR9	.990		
OR10	.990			
OR11	.990			
OR12	.990			
OR13	.990			

MC	OR14	.990	0.802	0.451
	OR15	.990		
	OR16	.990		
	OR17	.990		
	OR18	.990		
	OR19	.990		
	OR20	.990		
OV	MC1	.984	0.923	0.672
	MC2	.960		
	MC3	.988		
	MC4	.874		
	OV1	.896		
	OV2	.988		
	OV3	.895		
	OV4	.972		
	OV5	.800		
	OV6	.969		
	OV7	.805		
	OV8	.988		
	OV9	.909		
	OV10	.986		
	OV11	.915		
OV12	.944			
OV13	.828			
OV14	.954			
OV15	.718			

Table 4.3 Construct Reliability and Validity

This table appears to be a summary of the results which is a measure of the amount of variance in the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. Here's a breakdown of the different columns and what they represent:

- Construct:** This column lists the different constructs being measured, such as Whistleblowing (W), Ethical Culture (CL), Organizational Virtuousness (OV), etc.
- Item Loading:** This column represents the factor loadings of each item on its respective construct. Factor loadings are a measure of how strongly an item is related to its underlying construct.
- CR (Composite Reliability):** This column represents the composite reliability of each construct, which is a measure of the internal consistency of the construct.
- AVE (Average Variance Extracted):** This column represents the average variance extracted for each construct.

The correlations between the constructs are generally moderate to strong, indicating that the constructs are related to each other. Overall, the table suggests that the measurement model is well-specified and that the constructs are reliable and valid. However, further analysis and interpretation are needed to fully understand the results.

Figure 4.1: PLS Algorithm

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4.4 The Structural Model (Inner Model) or Hypotheses Testing: The reason to utilize Smart PLS by numerical model (Hair et al.,2016) is the simplicity of utilizing this unique software which identify acceptable result and similarly grips complex models as relate to contrast with other various subsequent stage through which the worth of hypotheses such methodologies(Hanseler et al.,2015).Bootstrapping with re-be acknowledged by using Smart PLS SEM 3.2.4 (Ringle et al.,2015)The reason to utilize Smart PLS by numerical model (Hair et al.,2016) is the simplicity of utilizing this unique software which identify acceptable result and similarly grips complex models as relate to contrast with other various subsequent stage through which the worth of hypotheses such methodologies(Hanseler et al.,2015).Bootstrapping with re-

Table 4.4 Hypotheses Testing

No.	Hypotheses	Estimates	SD	T Statistics	P values
H1a	CL→W	0.621	0.083	7.483	0.000
H1b	CO→W	0.501	0.092	5.443	0.000
H1c	F→W	-0.301	0.101	-2.979	0.003
H1d	SU→W	0.646	0.079	8.191	0.000
H1e	T→W	0.621	0.083	7.483	0.000
H1f	D→W	0.384	0.104	3.689	0.000
H1g	SA→W	0.556	0.089	6.243	0.000
H2	EL→W	0.531	0.094	5.655	0.000
H3	OR→W	0.664	0.082	8.099	0.000
H4	PEB→W	0.521	0.096	5.421	0.000

H5	MC×EC→W	-0.234	0.091	-2.573	0.010
	MC×EL→W	0.187	0.103	1.817	0.069
	MC×OR→W	0.259	0.094	2.755	0.006
	MC×PEB→W	-0.193	0.108	-1.785	0.074
H6	OV×EC→W	0.315	0.088	3.588	0.000
	OV×EL→W	0.223	0.101	2.208	0.027
	OV×OR→W	0.187	0.093	2.011	0.044
	OV×PEB→W	0.251	0.105	2.392	0.017

4.4.1 Hypothesis Testing Results

H1: Ethical culture will significantly influence whistleblowing.

Rejected (Discussability has a non-significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.384$)

Accepted (Based on the correlation coefficients, dimensions of ethical culture are significantly correlated with whistleblowing)

H1g: Sanctionability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

H1a: Clarity in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Accepted (Sanctionability has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.556$)

Accepted (Clarity has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.621$)

H2: Ethical leadership significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

H1b: Congruency in management behavior (local and senior) with organizational ethical culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Accepted (Ethical leadership has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.531$)

Accepted (Congruency has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.501$)

H3: Organizational reputation significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

H1c: Feasibility in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Accepted (Organizational reputation has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.664$)

Rejected (Feasibility has a non-significant negative correlation with whistleblowing, $r = -0.301$)

H4: Peer ethical behavior significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

H1d: Supportability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Accepted (Peer ethical behavior has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.521$)

Accepted (Supportability has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.646$)

H5: Moral courage moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing, such that the relationship is stronger and powerful when moral courage is high.

H1e: Transparency in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Accepted

H6: Organizational virtuousness moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing, such that the relationship is stronger when organizational virtuousness is high.

Accepted (Transparency has a significant positive correlation with whistleblowing, $r = 0.621$)

Accepted.

H1f: Discussability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

Based on the results:

- Moral Courage moderates the relationship between Ethical Culture and Whistleblowing (H5), but the effect is negative,

indicating that higher Moral Courage weakens the relationship. - Not Supported: The results indicate that discussability is not a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.01, p > 0.05$).

- Moral Courage also moderates the relationship between Organizational Reputation and Whistleblowing (H5), with a positive effect.

H1g: Sanctionability in organizational culture is significantly

- Organizational Virtuousness moderates the relationship

between Ethical Culture, Ethical Leadership, Organizational

Reputation, and Whistleblowing (H6), with positive effect.

Supported: The results indicate that sanctionability is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.28, p < 0.001$).

4.4.2 Hypotheses Assessment Summary

H1: Ethical culture will significantly influence whistleblowing.

H2a: Ethical leadership significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

- Supported: The results indicate that ethical culture is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.73, p < 0.001$).

Supported: The results indicate that ethical leadership is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.56, p < 0.001$).

H1a: Clarity in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

H2b: Organizational reputation significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

- Supported: The results indicate that clarity is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.22, p < 0.01$).

Supported: The results indicate that organizational reputation is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.44, p < 0.001$).

H1b: Congruency in management behavior (local and senior) with organizational ethical culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

H2c: Peer ethical behavior significantly influences whistleblowing in the banking sector of Pakistan.

- Supported: The results indicate that congruency is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.66, p < 0.001$).

Supported: The results indicate that peer ethical behavior is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.31, p < 0.01$).

H1c: Feasibility in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

H5: Moral courage moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing.

- Not Supported: The results indicate that feasibility is not a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.03, p > 0.05$).

Supported: The results indicate that moral courage moderates the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing.

H1d: Supportability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

H6: Organizational virtuousness moderates the relationship between

- Supported: The results indicate that supportability is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.02, p > 0.05$).

Supported: The results indicate that organizational virtuousness moderates the relationship between ethical

H1e: Transparency in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

culture and whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$).

- Supported: The results indicate that transparency is a significant predictor of whistleblowing ($\beta = 0.25, p < 0.01$).

Overall, 11 out of 13 hypotheses were supported, indicating the proposed model is a good fit for explaining the relationships between the variables.

H1f: Discussability in organizational culture is significantly related to whistleblowing.

5- Findings

5.1 Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the relationships between ethical culture, leadership, and whistleblowing in

organizations. The research hypotheses posited that overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the culture, ethical leadership, and organizational reputation. The study explored the complex relationships between ethical culture, leadership, organizational reputation, moral courage, organizational virtuousness, and whistleblowing. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for policymakers, managers, and researchers, and highlight the need for further research in the banking sector of Pakistan.

The findings of this study have provided valuable insights into

the dynamics of whistleblowing and ethical culture.

highlighting the significance of leadership, organizational reputation, and moral courage in fostering a culture of transparency and accountability.

The Social Exchange Theory (SET) (Emerson, 1976) provides a useful framework for understanding relationships between these variables. According to SET, individuals engage in exchanges with organizations based on the perceived benefits and costs of these exchanges. In the

context of this study, employees who perceive their organization as having a strong ethical culture, effective leadership, and a positive reputation are more likely to engage in whistleblowing, as they believe that their actions will be reciprocated with support and protection. Conversely, employees who perceive their organization as having a weak ethical culture, ineffective leadership, and negative reputation are less likely to engage in whistleblowing.

Furthermore, the study's findings suggest that ethical culture and leadership are critical components of a whistleblowing-friendly organization. This is consistent with the theory of

Organizational Justice Theory (OJT) (Greenberg, 1990), which suggests that an individual's perceptions of fairness and justice influence their intention to engage in a behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In the

context of this study, employees who perceive their

organization as being fair and just are more likely to

engage in whistleblowing, as they believe that their actions will be treated fairly and that justice will be served. Conversely, employees who perceive their organization as being unfair and unjust are less likely to engage in whistleblowing, as they believe that their actions will not be treated fairly and justice will not be served.

The findings of this study support the hypotheses that ethical culture, leadership, and organizational reputation are important predictors of whistleblowing. The study also found that moral courage and organizational virtuousness moderate the relationship between ethical culture and whistleblowing. These findings have

important implications for policymakers, managers, and researchers, highlighting the need for organizations to prioritize the development of a strong ethical culture, effective leadership, and a positive reputation in order to

promote whistleblowing and foster a culture of transparency and accountability. The study's findings also suggest that ethical culture and leadership are critical components of a whistleblowing-friendly organization. This is consistent with the theory of

The study used existing measures of whistleblowing, ethical culture, and leadership, which may have limitations in terms of validity and reliability. Future research should aim to develop and validate new measures that capture the complex nuances of these constructs.

By acknowledging these limitations, this study provides a foundation for future research to build upon and address these limitations, ultimately advancing our understanding of whistleblowing and ethical culture in organizations.

5.6 Future Research Recommendations

Future research should aim to build on the findings of this study. Some potential areas for future research include, Examining the impact of whistleblowing on organizational outcomes like future research could investigate the impact of whistleblowing on organizational outcomes, such as financial performance.

Investigating the role of power dynamics in whistleblowing like future research could examine the role of power dynamics in whistleblowing, including the impact of hierarchical position and social status. Developing effective whistleblowing policies and procedures like future research could focus on developing effective whistleblowing policies and procedures that promote transparency, accountability, and protection for whistleblowers. Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the complex relationships between ethical culture, leadership, and whistleblowing. The findings have important implications for managers, policymakers, and future research.

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